

TIGER: Temporally Improved Graph Entity Linker Supplementary Material

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1. DATASET CONSTRUCTION

We combined the TempEL¹ dataset, a benchmark for temporal entity linking, with Wikidata5M² to explore the benefits of structured knowledge graphs. Our resultant dataset has five segments: two text-based (**entity description** and **mention context**) and three graph-based (**structure graph**, **feature graph**, and **feature matrix**). Both the structure and feature graphs depict yearly entity relationships. Continual entities refer to existing entities in previous years, and new entities refer to newly appeared, previously non-existent entities. The construction process is shown in Figure S1, with detailed steps provided in supplementary material. We will make the dataset and code available in the GitHub repository after our paper is accepted. We now walk through each step. We now walk through each step.

Fig. S1. Dataset construction process.

First, we categorized each year of data from the TempEL dataset into entity descriptions and mention context parts based on the year. The entity description comprises the title, text, document ID, and, importantly, the unique ID of the entity (its QID). The mention context consists of context left, context right, mention, label, QID, and category.

Second, we create a structure graph based on the relationship in the Wikidata5M dataset and the entity IDs in the TempEL dataset. There are numerous relationships among entities in the Wikidata5M dataset. To filter down the number of relationships, we matched these relationships' entity IDs (also QIDs) with the

¹<https://cloud.ilabt.imec.be/index.php/s/RinXy8NgqdW58RW>

²<https://deepgraphlearning.github.io/project/wikidata5m>

QID in the entity descriptions from the TempEL dataset. We will keep the relationship if both QIDs are in a relationship in the Wikidata5M data and are present in the existing entity description. The structure graph is an $n \times n$ adjacency matrix, where n represents the total number of entities in the dataset. Each row indicates whether an entity has a connection with another entity. The adjacency matrix is made up of 0s and 1s. If entity i and entity j are connected, the value in the i^{th} row and j^{th} column of the matrix is 1; otherwise, it is 0.

Note that, at this point, we may have introduced temporal leakage. This is because the cutoff for the Wikidata5M dataset is July 2019. If we construct a structure graph based on Wikidata5M, temporal leakage might occur when dealing with data from years prior to 2019. For instance, if entity 1 and entity 2 had no relationship in 2013 but established one in 2019, our construction of the 2013 structure graph would inevitably link entity 1 and entity 2. However, the efficacy of our model can still be demonstrated. For example, when we only use data from 2019 to 2022, our model demonstrates a 16.24% performance boost over the state-of-the-art in a temporal setting when the time gap is one year and an improvement to 20.93% as the gap expands to three years.

Third, we built the feature graph using the embeddings from entity descriptions. We employed the pre-trained bert-base-uncased model to embed the entity description’s textual information associated with the "text" key. By accessing the embedded information for each entity in the dataset, we established a k NN graph based on these entities, which we refer to as the feature graph. This graph highlights the connections between entities based on their entity descriptions. The feature graph is also an $n \times n$ adjacency matrix, where n represents the total number of entities in the dataset. Each row indicates whether an entity has a connection with other entities. If entity i and entity j are connected, the value in the i^{th} row and j^{th} column of the matrix is 1; otherwise, it is 0.

The difference between connections in the structure graph and those in the feature graph is that the connections in the structure graph are constructed based on actual existing links. For instance, on the Wikipedia page for "*Weightlifting (Q83462)*", the "*Summer Olympic Games (Q212434)*" is mentioned in the first two paragraphs. Hence, a connection between these two entities exists in the structure graph. However, connections in the feature graph are generated based on the embeddings of entity descriptions, which might not exist in the KG but can still benefit the model. For example, while "*Arizona Wildcats (Q4620330)*" and "*Summer Olympic Games (Q212434)*" are not directly related, the embeddings of their descriptions have created a link between them. This makes "*Arizona Wildcats (Q4620330)*" less likely to be confused with "*Arizona (Q816)*" or "*Wildcats (Q26665)*" a 1986 film by Michael Ritchie.

Fourth, we constructed a feature matrix representing each entity based on the tokens from entity descriptions in the dataset. After getting the token IDs for each entity using the pre-trained bert-base-uncased model, we filtered all token IDs based on their frequency of occurrence. We retained those token IDs that appeared between 46 and 200 times. We discarded highly frequent token IDs since these tokens, such as "is," "an," "the," and other common words, do not offer meaningful differentiation among entities. Also, the less frequent token IDs were removed due to the possibility of them being meaningless noise or random codes, and including an excess of these rare tokens would make the matrix too sparse, slowing down computation. The final feature matrix is an $n \times m$ dimensional matrix composed of 0s and 1s. Here, n represents the total number of entities in the dataset, while m is the number of retained token IDs. If the data in the i^{th} row and j^{th} column of the matrix is 1, it indicates that entity i contains the j^{th} token.

Finally, we generate distinct mention context subsets from all available mention context samples. Using the "category" in each sample as the standard, we further divided the training set into two sub-training sets: "Continual entities (existing entities in previous years)" and "New entities (newly appeared, previously non-existent entities)."

2. TRAINING DETAILS

Parameter Settings. We reuse the same hyperparameter settings from BLINK model and the same bert_uncased_L-8_H-512_A-8 pre-trained model to train the bi-encoder. The recall@ N is used as the evaluation metric, where N equals 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, and 64, respectively. If the correct answer appears within the top N predictions of the model, it is considered a correct prediction. The bi-encoder is trained on the ZESHEL dataset across five epochs, utilizing 128 mentions and 128 entity tokens at a learning rate 1e-05. Conversely, the bi-encoder undergoes training for one epoch on our dataset, maintaining similar mention and entity token quantities and learning rates. The training process employs an annual training approach and tests on all test sets. For instance, the results for 2019 are obtained by training on the 2019 training set and validating on the 2019 validation set. Once trained, the model is then saved. Subsequently, testing is performed on the test sets spanning the four years from 2019 to 2022.

Training Environment. Software versions: Python 3.9.16; PyTorch 1.7.1+cu110; Faiss-GPU 1.6.5; Numpy 1.24.2; SciPy 1.10.1; scikit-learn 1.2.1. All the experiments were run on a single A100 GPU with 40GB RAM.

3. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - NEW ENTITIES TRAINING SET

Tables S1 through Table S7 present a comparison between the baseline models (BLINK and SpEL) and our model TIGER. The dataset, "Extended TempEL: New entities," has a training set (1,764), a validation set ($\approx 42k$, same as original TempEL dataset), and a test set ($\approx 48k$, same as original TempEL dataset). Here, the training set contains only 1,764 samples because, in the original TempEL dataset, each year's dataset contains only 1,764 'new entities' samples. Rows represent training datasets, while columns represent testing datasets. For example, the number at the intersection of the first row and the tenth column in Table S1 is 0.1433, showing the model's performance when trained on 2013 data and tested on 2022 data. Performance evaluations for all models were based on recall metrics, specifically @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32, and @64.

Table S1. Results between our model and the baseline models @1 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.1440	0.1435	0.1431	0.1459	0.1473	0.1450	0.1431	0.1477	0.1445	0.1433	
	2014	0.1221	0.1229	0.1229	0.1235	0.1222	0.1220	0.1202	0.1260	0.1228	0.1246	
	2015	0.1380	0.1359	0.1371	0.1384	0.1397	0.1373	0.1371	0.1412	0.1376	0.1366	
	2016	0.1310	0.1320	0.1308	0.1321	0.1330	0.1304	0.1314	0.1349	0.1316	0.1326	
	2017	0.1403	0.1404	0.1404	0.1415	0.1428	0.1424	0.1402	0.1438	0.1410	0.1422	
	2018	0.1284	0.1269	0.1268	0.1268	0.1301	0.1276	0.1284	0.1306	0.1268	0.1270	
	2019	0.1400	0.1397	0.1418	0.1415	0.1427	0.1411	0.1409	0.1449	0.1406	0.1424	
	2020	0.1228	0.1231	0.1206	0.1228	0.1245	0.1224	0.1206	0.1261	0.1216	0.1238	
	2021	0.1270	0.1267	0.1270	0.1265	0.1271	0.1243	0.1239	0.1303	0.1294	0.1305	
	2022	0.1266	0.1264	0.1264	0.1275	0.1297	0.1271	0.1265	0.1313	0.1288	0.1300	
SpEL	2013	0.1740	0.1735	0.1931	0.1759	0.1773	0.1950	0.1831	0.1777	0.1945	0.1933	
	2014	0.1721	0.1529	0.1729	0.1735	0.1622	0.1520	0.1502	0.1760	0.1728	0.1646	
	2015	0.1680	0.1659	0.1771	0.1784	0.1797	0.1873	0.1671	0.1812	0.1676	0.1866	
	2016	0.1610	0.1820	0.1708	0.1821	0.1630	0.1604	0.1714	0.1749	0.1616	0.1626	
	2017	0.1803	0.1804	0.1804	0.1815	0.1828	0.1724	0.1902	0.1838	0.1810	0.1722	
	2018	0.1684	0.1569	0.1668	0.1568	0.1601	0.1776	0.1584	0.1806	0.1668	0.1670	
	2019	0.1800	0.1697	0.1718	0.1915	0.1727	0.1811	0.1809	0.1849	0.1706	0.1924	
	2020	0.1628	0.1731	0.1606	0.1728	0.1545	0.1724	0.1706	0.1661	0.1516	0.1638	
	2021	0.1770	0.1567	0.1770	0.1765	0.1671	0.1643	0.1739	0.1603	0.1794	0.1705	
	2022	0.1566	0.1564	0.1464	0.1475	0.1497	0.1571	0.1565	0.1613	0.1488	0.1600	
TIGER	2013	0.2245	0.2242	0.2257	0.2299	0.2283	0.2290	0.2245	0.2285	0.2294	0.2304	
	2014	0.2011	0.2022	0.2011	0.2029	0.2062	0.2019	0.2010	0.2048	0.2031	0.2003	
	2015	0.2307	0.2320	0.2313	0.2319	0.2355	0.2349	0.2343	0.2359	0.2355	0.2346	
	2016	0.2154	0.2185	0.2161	0.2206	0.2206	0.2208	0.2180	0.2222	0.2185	0.2197	
	2017	0.2292	0.2306	0.2297	0.2313	0.2335	0.2328	0.2313	0.2330	0.2320	0.2318	
	2018	0.1725	0.1707	0.1710	0.1706	0.1753	0.1740	0.1738	0.1768	0.1750	0.1762	
	2019	0.2156	0.2195	0.2172	0.2166	0.2208	0.2198	0.2174	0.2158	0.2156	0.2169	
	2020	0.1570	0.1550	0.1573	0.1579	0.1606	0.1604	0.1591	0.1627	0.1604	0.1605	
	2021	0.2012	0.2025	0.2013	0.2057	0.2049	0.2084	0.2049	0.2072	0.2079	0.2076	
	2022	0.1523	0.1529	0.1548	0.1579	0.1598	0.1590	0.1566	0.1589	0.1566	0.1574	

Table S2. Results between our model and the baseline models @2 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2131	0.2141	0.2136	0.2139	0.2156	0.2157	0.2141	0.2182	0.2133	0.2117	
	2014	0.1845	0.1850	0.1839	0.1840	0.1851	0.1841	0.1809	0.1858	0.1826	0.1858	
	2015	0.2035	0.2035	0.2061	0.2059	0.2072	0.2064	0.2053	0.2083	0.2048	0.2034	
	2016	0.1987	0.1983	0.1972	0.1985	0.1999	0.1983	0.1955	0.2007	0.1965	0.1990	
	2017	0.2099	0.2100	0.2103	0.2117	0.2129	0.2133	0.2092	0.2133	0.2109	0.2119	
	2018	0.1902	0.1910	0.1928	0.1916	0.1937	0.1917	0.1915	0.1942	0.1896	0.1912	
	2019	0.2073	0.2079	0.2109	0.2112	0.2123	0.2128	0.2087	0.2137	0.2092	0.2108	
	2020	0.1862	0.1855	0.1848	0.1853	0.1891	0.1871	0.1838	0.1896	0.1844	0.1871	
	2021	0.1910	0.1926	0.1900	0.1908	0.1915	0.1892	0.1868	0.1938	0.1945	0.1927	
	2022	0.1912	0.1917	0.1909	0.1915	0.1943	0.1911	0.1889	0.1951	0.1925	0.1937	
SpEL	2013	0.2531	0.2541	0.2536	0.2739	0.2656	0.2657	0.2541	0.2582	0.2633	0.2617	
	2014	0.2445	0.2250	0.2339	0.2340	0.2351	0.2341	0.2209	0.2358	0.2226	0.2358	
	2015	0.2435	0.2635	0.2461	0.2459	0.2472	0.2564	0.2553	0.2483	0.2548	0.2634	
	2016	0.2387	0.2483	0.2472	0.2485	0.2399	0.2483	0.2455	0.2507	0.2365	0.2490	
	2017	0.2499	0.2700	0.2503	0.2717	0.2729	0.2633	0.2592	0.2533	0.2509	0.2519	
	2018	0.2502	0.2510	0.2328	0.2516	0.2437	0.2417	0.2315	0.2442	0.2496	0.2512	
	2019	0.2473	0.2479	0.2609	0.2612	0.2623	0.2528	0.2587	0.2537	0.2692	0.2608	
	2020	0.2262	0.2255	0.2248	0.2353	0.2491	0.2271	0.2338	0.2296	0.2344	0.2471	
	2021	0.2510	0.2526	0.2500	0.2408	0.2315	0.2392	0.2268	0.2338	0.2545	0.2527	
	2022	0.2112	0.2217	0.2109	0.2215	0.2143	0.2211	0.2089	0.2251	0.2225	0.2137	
TIGER	2013	0.3213	0.3242	0.3235	0.3286	0.3276	0.3280	0.3208	0.3250	0.3280	0.3301	
	2014	0.2921	0.2935	0.2910	0.2928	0.2956	0.2938	0.2919	0.2954	0.2958	0.2924	
	2015	0.3283	0.3286	0.3306	0.3317	0.3361	0.3357	0.3302	0.3327	0.3345	0.3347	
	2016	0.3113	0.3125	0.3148	0.3160	0.3181	0.3167	0.3158	0.3172	0.3161	0.3159	
	2017	0.3270	0.3290	0.3290	0.3303	0.3326	0.3296	0.3275	0.3300	0.3293	0.3316	
	2018	0.2555	0.2545	0.2556	0.2569	0.2594	0.2590	0.2584	0.2632	0.2601	0.2627	
	2019	0.3103	0.3134	0.3139	0.3137	0.3160	0.3146	0.3121	0.3111	0.3124	0.3138	
	2020	0.2346	0.2338	0.2362	0.2365	0.2409	0.2414	0.2394	0.2424	0.2434	0.2420	
	2021	0.2924	0.2964	0.2936	0.2967	0.3005	0.3009	0.2979	0.3013	0.3026	0.3002	
	2022	0.2314	0.2336	0.2355	0.2366	0.2396	0.2390	0.2382	0.2407	0.2367	0.2383	

Table S3. Results between our model and the baseline models @4 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2953	0.2951	0.2971	0.2986	0.3001	0.2994	0.2973	0.3010	0.2961	0.2952	
	2014	0.2583	0.2599	0.2584	0.2591	0.2620	0.2610	0.2587	0.2612	0.2581	0.2609	
	2015	0.2847	0.2836	0.2856	0.2861	0.2882	0.2866	0.2848	0.2889	0.2840	0.2847	
	2016	0.2774	0.2778	0.2794	0.2782	0.2808	0.2795	0.2749	0.2788	0.2768	0.2784	
	2017	0.2908	0.2935	0.2943	0.2943	0.2976	0.2948	0.2924	0.2955	0.2919	0.2946	
	2018	0.2689	0.2676	0.2674	0.2682	0.2697	0.2700	0.2652	0.2703	0.2654	0.2685	
	2019	0.2912	0.2933	0.2930	0.2927	0.2946	0.2941	0.2926	0.2951	0.2914	0.2944	
	2020	0.2642	0.2633	0.2641	0.2654	0.2683	0.2661	0.2648	0.2680	0.2627	0.2649	
	2021	0.2686	0.2701	0.2699	0.2690	0.2715	0.2698	0.2663	0.2722	0.2739	0.2719	
	2022	0.2707	0.2706	0.2705	0.2718	0.2728	0.2712	0.2684	0.2741	0.2719	0.2731	
SpEL	2013	0.3553	0.3551	0.3471	0.3586	0.3701	0.3694	0.3673	0.3710	0.3561	0.3652	
	2014	0.3183	0.3099	0.3084	0.3291	0.3120	0.3310	0.3287	0.3312	0.3081	0.3209	
	2015	0.3547	0.3336	0.3356	0.3561	0.3382	0.3466	0.3448	0.3489	0.3340	0.3547	
	2016	0.3274	0.3278	0.3294	0.3282	0.3508	0.3495	0.3349	0.3288	0.3268	0.3284	
	2017	0.3608	0.3635	0.3443	0.3443	0.3576	0.3648	0.3424	0.3455	0.3419	0.3546	
	2018	0.3289	0.3276	0.3174	0.3182	0.3197	0.3200	0.3152	0.3303	0.3254	0.3385	
	2019	0.3412	0.3633	0.3630	0.3627	0.3646	0.3441	0.3626	0.3651	0.3414	0.3544	
	2020	0.3342	0.3333	0.3341	0.3254	0.3183	0.3261	0.3248	0.3280	0.3127	0.3249	
	2021	0.3386	0.3201	0.3299	0.3390	0.3415	0.3198	0.3263	0.3322	0.3239	0.3419	
	2022	0.3107	0.2906	0.2905	0.2918	0.2928	0.3112	0.3084	0.3041	0.3019	0.3031	
TIGER	2013	0.4288	0.4313	0.4336	0.4378	0.4353	0.4334	0.4295	0.4337	0.4338	0.4376	
	2014	0.3923	0.3961	0.3930	0.3965	0.3975	0.3961	0.3940	0.3979	0.3968	0.3940	
	2015	0.4343	0.4380	0.4394	0.4391	0.4407	0.4417	0.4384	0.4394	0.4417	0.4427	
	2016	0.4165	0.4181	0.4187	0.4207	0.4211	0.4227	0.4205	0.4223	0.4198	0.4202	
	2017	0.4310	0.4348	0.4340	0.4346	0.4365	0.4343	0.4327	0.4369	0.4339	0.4386	
	2018	0.3523	0.3531	0.3525	0.3543	0.3566	0.3555	0.3531	0.3595	0.3574	0.3599	
	2019	0.4156	0.4190	0.4170	0.4191	0.4203	0.4190	0.4163	0.4176	0.4195	0.4210	
	2020	0.3302	0.3312	0.3334	0.3374	0.3378	0.3395	0.3361	0.3391	0.3425	0.3425	
	2021	0.3949	0.3993	0.3984	0.4011	0.4045	0.4006	0.4017	0.4043	0.4072	0.4062	
	2022	0.3268	0.3294	0.3289	0.3325	0.3355	0.3351	0.3330	0.3358	0.3348	0.3349	

Table S4. Results between our model and the baseline models @8 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test										
Train		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
BLINK	2013	0.3888	0.3892	0.3913	0.3942	0.3937	0.3918	0.3910	0.3918	0.3881	0.3883	
	2014	0.3485	0.3489	0.3502	0.3499	0.3507	0.3494	0.3474	0.3492	0.3471	0.3493	
	2015	0.3754	0.3761	0.3792	0.3788	0.3819	0.3779	0.3745	0.3767	0.3747	0.3750	
	2016	0.3711	0.3693	0.3717	0.3715	0.3734	0.3716	0.3686	0.3720	0.3694	0.3704	
	2017	0.3862	0.3886	0.3900	0.3889	0.3917	0.3881	0.3862	0.3888	0.3872	0.3871	
	2018	0.3604	0.3596	0.3598	0.3587	0.3600	0.3588	0.3553	0.3600	0.3545	0.3573	
	2019	0.3860	0.3895	0.3892	0.3911	0.3906	0.3904	0.3875	0.3901	0.3885	0.3915	
	2020	0.3538	0.3558	0.3591	0.3589	0.3606	0.3573	0.3559	0.3603	0.3558	0.3585	
	2021	0.3604	0.3604	0.3620	0.3612	0.3644	0.3636	0.3584	0.3654	0.3688	0.3640	
	2022	0.3619	0.3631	0.3634	0.3642	0.3653	0.3628	0.3620	0.3655	0.3649	0.3646	
SpEL	2013	0.4488	0.4692	0.4613	0.4642	0.4637	0.4618	0.4610	0.4618	0.4581	0.4483	
	2014	0.4185	0.4289	0.4102	0.4199	0.4207	0.4094	0.4074	0.4292	0.4071	0.4293	
	2015	0.4554	0.4561	0.4592	0.4488	0.4619	0.4379	0.4545	0.4567	0.4447	0.4450	
	2016	0.4511	0.4493	0.4417	0.4415	0.4534	0.4316	0.4386	0.4420	0.4294	0.4404	
	2017	0.4562	0.4586	0.4700	0.4489	0.4617	0.4581	0.4662	0.4588	0.4472	0.4671	
	2018	0.4304	0.4296	0.4298	0.4387	0.4400	0.4388	0.4353	0.4200	0.4145	0.4373	
	2019	0.4460	0.4695	0.4592	0.4611	0.4706	0.4604	0.4475	0.4701	0.4585	0.4715	
	2020	0.4338	0.4158	0.4391	0.4389	0.4406	0.4373	0.4259	0.4203	0.4158	0.4185	
	2021	0.4304	0.4404	0.4320	0.4312	0.4244	0.4236	0.4184	0.4354	0.4288	0.4340	
	2022	0.3919	0.3931	0.4034	0.4142	0.4053	0.4028	0.4020	0.3955	0.3949	0.3946	
TIGER	2013	0.5369	0.5393	0.5416	0.5448	0.5431	0.5412	0.5384	0.5411	0.5428	0.5453	
	2014	0.4959	0.4968	0.4980	0.5002	0.5016	0.5004	0.5000	0.5015	0.5015	0.5002	
	2015	0.5429	0.5471	0.5489	0.5493	0.5519	0.5488	0.5472	0.5465	0.5482	0.5506	
	2016	0.5237	0.5255	0.5255	0.5282	0.5291	0.5276	0.5257	0.5283	0.5300	0.5310	
	2017	0.5377	0.5414	0.5380	0.5405	0.5452	0.5409	0.5414	0.5459	0.5435	0.5451	
	2018	0.4578	0.4593	0.4599	0.4610	0.4631	0.4607	0.4596	0.4635	0.4639	0.4662	
	2019	0.5293	0.5284	0.5292	0.5328	0.5324	0.5308	0.5292	0.5310	0.5303	0.5330	
	2020	0.4387	0.4388	0.4413	0.4471	0.4448	0.4452	0.4444	0.4453	0.4482	0.4498	
	2021	0.5034	0.5063	0.5060	0.5095	0.5126	0.5089	0.5094	0.5125	0.5165	0.5145	
	2022	0.4336	0.4363	0.4376	0.4403	0.4420	0.4405	0.4399	0.4407	0.4405	0.4427	

Table S5. Results between our model and the baseline models @16 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.4861	0.4869	0.4897	0.4907	0.4933	0.4906	0.4878	0.4884	0.4846	0.4848	
	2014	0.4452	0.4476	0.4477	0.4479	0.4494	0.4486	0.4469	0.4492	0.4449	0.4474	
	2015	0.4728	0.4760	0.4768	0.4782	0.4785	0.4767	0.4715	0.4719	0.4699	0.4711	
	2016	0.4708	0.4709	0.4737	0.4729	0.4747	0.4737	0.4702	0.4712	0.4690	0.4702	
	2017	0.4834	0.4867	0.4886	0.4883	0.4893	0.4894	0.4864	0.4871	0.4849	0.4856	
	2018	0.4559	0.4585	0.4589	0.4599	0.4584	0.4580	0.4548	0.4556	0.4513	0.4536	
	2019	0.4884	0.4922	0.4928	0.4931	0.4947	0.4933	0.4921	0.4918	0.4913	0.4908	
	2020	0.4561	0.4580	0.4608	0.4618	0.4625	0.4611	0.4582	0.4591	0.4557	0.4561	
	2021	0.4611	0.4608	0.4633	0.4626	0.4671	0.4655	0.4613	0.4634	0.4696	0.4652	
	2022	0.4600	0.4644	0.4641	0.4643	0.4671	0.4639	0.4635	0.4642	0.4630	0.4657	
SpEL	2013	0.5661	0.5669	0.5597	0.5707	0.5733	0.5506	0.5578	0.5484	0.5446	0.5448	
	2014	0.5252	0.5176	0.5077	0.5279	0.5194	0.5086	0.5069	0.5292	0.5249	0.5274	
	2015	0.5428	0.5460	0.5568	0.5582	0.5585	0.5467	0.5415	0.5519	0.5299	0.5511	
	2016	0.5308	0.5309	0.5437	0.5529	0.5547	0.5537	0.5502	0.5412	0.5490	0.5302	
	2017	0.5434	0.5467	0.5486	0.5483	0.5593	0.5494	0.5664	0.5671	0.5549	0.5656	
	2018	0.5359	0.5285	0.5289	0.5199	0.5384	0.5280	0.5248	0.5256	0.5113	0.5336	
	2019	0.5684	0.5522	0.5728	0.5631	0.5547	0.5733	0.5621	0.5618	0.5713	0.5508	
	2020	0.5261	0.5280	0.5308	0.5318	0.5425	0.5311	0.5282	0.5391	0.5257	0.5361	
	2021	0.5411	0.5208	0.5333	0.5326	0.5371	0.5455	0.5213	0.5334	0.5396	0.5352	
	2022	0.5100	0.5044	0.5141	0.5143	0.5071	0.5039	0.5135	0.5142	0.5030	0.5157	
TIGER	2013	0.6426	0.6422	0.6444	0.6444	0.6460	0.6460	0.6449	0.6441	0.6467	0.6489	
	2014	0.5986	0.6005	0.5999	0.5993	0.6022	0.5995	0.6027	0.6042	0.6030	0.6033	
	2015	0.6461	0.6503	0.6518	0.6510	0.6535	0.6497	0.6490	0.6487	0.6496	0.6530	
	2016	0.6302	0.6291	0.6324	0.6338	0.6342	0.6324	0.6325	0.6336	0.6352	0.6352	
	2017	0.6377	0.6403	0.6419	0.6412	0.6457	0.6412	0.6420	0.6446	0.6419	0.6437	
	2018	0.5651	0.5670	0.5682	0.5678	0.5687	0.5679	0.5652	0.5699	0.5690	0.5711	
	2019	0.6366	0.6373	0.6366	0.6376	0.6383	0.6366	0.6355	0.6354	0.6367	0.6376	
	2020	0.5506	0.5514	0.5516	0.5559	0.5575	0.5571	0.5575	0.5567	0.5587	0.5617	
	2021	0.6068	0.6109	0.6113	0.6111	0.6162	0.6115	0.6126	0.6141	0.6193	0.6189	
	2022	0.5459	0.5490	0.5509	0.5504	0.5548	0.5510	0.5514	0.5521	0.5539	0.5551	

Table S6. Results between our model and the baseline models @32 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.5882	0.5907	0.5918	0.5907	0.5920	0.5899	0.5871	0.5870	0.5832	0.5855	
	2014	0.5467	0.5505	0.5511	0.5507	0.5515	0.5509	0.5482	0.5491	0.5456	0.5471	
	2015	0.5722	0.5766	0.5781	0.5773	0.5780	0.5772	0.5744	0.5738	0.5706	0.5709	
	2016	0.5735	0.5771	0.5771	0.5760	0.5789	0.5761	0.5743	0.5738	0.5708	0.5715	
	2017	0.5854	0.5894	0.5892	0.5873	0.5914	0.5900	0.5874	0.5873	0.5843	0.5860	
	2018	0.5561	0.5588	0.5601	0.5587	0.5602	0.5598	0.5562	0.5563	0.5517	0.5536	
	2019	0.5925	0.5960	0.5976	0.5943	0.5981	0.5961	0.5967	0.5940	0.5934	0.5930	
	2020	0.5596	0.5627	0.5650	0.5640	0.5658	0.5647	0.5631	0.5642	0.5588	0.5606	
	2021	0.5644	0.5657	0.5675	0.5684	0.5716	0.5707	0.5696	0.5699	0.5765	0.5738	
	2022	0.5634	0.5679	0.5668	0.5677	0.5685	0.5679	0.5681	0.5677	0.5664	0.5660	
SpEL	2013	0.6582	0.6507	0.6518	0.6607	0.6520	0.6499	0.6471	0.6570	0.6432	0.6555	
	2014	0.6067	0.6205	0.6111	0.6107	0.6215	0.6309	0.6182	0.6091	0.6056	0.6271	
	2015	0.6322	0.6566	0.6481	0.6373	0.6480	0.6572	0.6444	0.6438	0.6406	0.6409	
	2016	0.6435	0.6571	0.6571	0.6360	0.6489	0.6361	0.6443	0.6538	0.6408	0.6515	
	2017	0.6554	0.6594	0.6692	0.6673	0.6514	0.6700	0.6674	0.6473	0.6443	0.6460	
	2018	0.6161	0.6188	0.6401	0.6287	0.6402	0.6298	0.6162	0.6263	0.6117	0.6136	
	2019	0.6525	0.6760	0.6776	0.6543	0.6681	0.6561	0.6567	0.6540	0.6534	0.6730	
	2020	0.6196	0.6227	0.6450	0.6340	0.6358	0.6247	0.6331	0.6342	0.6388	0.6206	
	2021	0.6444	0.6457	0.6275	0.6284	0.6416	0.6507	0.6496	0.6399	0.6565	0.6438	
	2022	0.6234	0.6179	0.6168	0.6177	0.6285	0.6279	0.6181	0.6277	0.6264	0.6160	
TIGER	2013	0.7365	0.7348	0.7381	0.7347	0.7379	0.7365	0.7360	0.7365	0.7396	0.7401	
	2014	0.6923	0.6938	0.6937	0.6924	0.6960	0.6954	0.6986	0.6991	0.6982	0.7016	
	2015	0.7367	0.7403	0.7406	0.7409	0.7429	0.7390	0.7377	0.7395	0.7398	0.7416	
	2016	0.7246	0.7258	0.7285	0.7288	0.7291	0.7267	0.7288	0.7304	0.7305	0.7300	
	2017	0.7287	0.7313	0.7327	0.7330	0.7371	0.7324	0.7332	0.7338	0.7324	0.7370	
	2018	0.6640	0.6657	0.6679	0.6672	0.6684	0.6688	0.6671	0.6688	0.6671	0.6702	
	2019	0.7290	0.7292	0.7315	0.7304	0.7330	0.7309	0.7313	0.7283	0.7310	0.7320	
	2020	0.6629	0.6651	0.6661	0.6649	0.6698	0.6695	0.6700	0.6686	0.6713	0.6721	
	2021	0.7031	0.7066	0.7051	0.7061	0.7100	0.7082	0.7081	0.7107	0.7125	0.7125	
	2022	0.6540	0.6556	0.6598	0.6593	0.6616	0.6613	0.6617	0.6608	0.6594	0.6631	

Table S7. Results between our model and the baseline models @64 ("Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set).

		Test										
Train		2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	
BLINK	2013	0.6831	0.6858	0.6879	0.6850	0.6861	0.6867	0.6840	0.6834	0.6809	0.6832	
	2014	0.6499	0.6526	0.6516	0.6508	0.6523	0.6524	0.6495	0.6504	0.6471	0.6492	
	2015	0.6718	0.6747	0.6761	0.6746	0.6738	0.6729	0.6721	0.6705	0.6696	0.6705	
	2016	0.6745	0.6774	0.6775	0.6763	0.6784	0.6752	0.6747	0.6759	0.6743	0.6751	
	2017	0.6845	0.6867	0.6873	0.6850	0.6876	0.6876	0.6843	0.6849	0.6842	0.6859	
	2018	0.6583	0.6603	0.6617	0.6574	0.6600	0.6595	0.6582	0.6571	0.6554	0.6565	
	2019	0.6934	0.6954	0.6954	0.6949	0.6967	0.6953	0.6945	0.6921	0.6934	0.6939	
	2020	0.6642	0.6672	0.6676	0.6662	0.6676	0.6663	0.6658	0.6654	0.6632	0.6654	
	2021	0.6681	0.6702	0.6711	0.6708	0.6738	0.6730	0.6726	0.6713	0.6762	0.6736	
	2022	0.6639	0.6677	0.6690	0.6677	0.6705	0.6709	0.6691	0.6683	0.6707	0.6699	
SpEL	2013	0.7531	0.7558	0.7479	0.7350	0.7361	0.7367	0.7440	0.7334	0.7309	0.7432	
	2014	0.7199	0.7226	0.7216	0.7208	0.7223	0.7024	0.7195	0.7104	0.7071	0.7092	
	2015	0.7218	0.7347	0.7261	0.7346	0.7238	0.7429	0.7221	0.7305	0.7296	0.7405	
	2016	0.7445	0.7474	0.7375	0.7463	0.7484	0.7252	0.7447	0.7259	0.7443	0.7451	
	2017	0.7345	0.7567	0.7573	0.7450	0.7476	0.7376	0.7443	0.7549	0.7542	0.7459	
	2018	0.7083	0.7303	0.7117	0.7174	0.7100	0.7095	0.7182	0.7071	0.7054	0.7265	
	2019	0.7634	0.7554	0.7654	0.7549	0.7467	0.7553	0.7645	0.7621	0.7634	0.7539	
	2020	0.7242	0.7172	0.7376	0.7262	0.7176	0.7163	0.7258	0.7254	0.7132	0.7154	
	2021	0.7381	0.7402	0.7211	0.7208	0.7238	0.7430	0.7326	0.7313	0.7362	0.7236	
	2022	0.6939	0.6977	0.7090	0.7177	0.7205	0.7209	0.6991	0.7183	0.7007	0.6999	
TIGER	2013	0.8149	0.8136	0.8142	0.8136	0.8150	0.8132	0.8127	0.8136	0.8152	0.8169	
	2014	0.7751	0.7770	0.7781	0.7785	0.7787	0.7784	0.7789	0.7804	0.7797	0.7839	
	2015	0.8113	0.8149	0.8145	0.8146	0.8155	0.8129	0.8118	0.8137	0.8139	0.8156	
	2016	0.8048	0.8073	0.8106	0.8099	0.8121	0.8096	0.8099	0.8105	0.8101	0.8100	
	2017	0.8053	0.8068	0.8102	0.8096	0.8129	0.8086	0.8079	0.8098	0.8096	0.8128	
	2018	0.7523	0.7557	0.7575	0.7575	0.7605	0.7577	0.7571	0.7588	0.7575	0.7607	
	2019	0.8096	0.8106	0.8125	0.8111	0.8125	0.8110	0.8110	0.8090	0.8112	0.8130	
	2020	0.7597	0.7649	0.7642	0.7642	0.7663	0.7677	0.7679	0.7659	0.7671	0.7684	
	2021	0.7861	0.7882	0.7898	0.7878	0.7927	0.7899	0.7904	0.7926	0.7948	0.7955	
	2022	0.7513	0.7544	0.7569	0.7571	0.7579	0.7578	0.7581	0.7589	0.7582	0.7616	

4. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - CONTINUAL ENTITIES TRAINING SET

Tables S8 through Table S14 present a comparison between the baseline models (BLINK and SpEL) and our model TIGER. The dataset, "Extended TempEL: Continual entities," has a training set (1,764), a validation set ($\approx 42k$, same as original TempEL dataset), and a test set ($\approx 48k$, same as original TempEL dataset). Here, the training set contains only 1,764 samples because, in the original TempEL dataset, each year's dataset contains only 1,764 'new entities' samples. For comparison, we also have 1,764 'continual entity' samples. Rows represent training datasets, while columns represent testing datasets. For example, the number at the intersection of the first row and the tenth column in Table S8 is 0.1741, showing the model's performance when trained on 2013 data and tested on 2022 data. Performance evaluations for all models were based on recall metrics, specifically @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32, and @64.

Table S8. Results between our model and the baseline models @1 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.1710	0.1719	0.1712	0.1727	0.1719	0.1736	0.1701	0.1761	0.1743	0.1741	
	2014	0.1585	0.1593	0.1598	0.1613	0.1608	0.1587	0.1584	0.1625	0.1621	0.1620	
	2015	0.1854	0.1870	0.1878	0.1879	0.1897	0.1887	0.1855	0.1913	0.1898	0.1909	
	2016	0.1581	0.1589	0.1579	0.1595	0.1609	0.1602	0.1575	0.1614	0.1597	0.1589	
	2017	0.1926	0.1953	0.1950	0.1947	0.1961	0.1944	0.1901	0.1984	0.1952	0.1944	
	2018	0.1797	0.1782	0.1779	0.1786	0.1774	0.1799	0.1760	0.1833	0.1817	0.1801	
	2019	0.1757	0.1767	0.1766	0.1763	0.1775	0.1775	0.1729	0.1785	0.1783	0.1774	
	2020	0.1841	0.1867	0.1873	0.1869	0.1890	0.1874	0.1843	0.1901	0.1875	0.1866	
	2021	0.1759	0.1752	0.1742	0.1760	0.1769	0.1754	0.1735	0.1797	0.1771	0.1758	
	2022	0.1623	0.1641	0.1645	0.1666	0.1673	0.1656	0.1634	0.1686	0.1665	0.1665	
SpEL	2013	0.2275	0.2133	0.2269	0.2133	0.2296	0.2237	0.2130	0.2284	0.2153	0.2264	
	2014	0.2039	0.2160	0.2065	0.2179	0.2095	0.2091	0.2041	0.2191	0.2078	0.2213	
	2015	0.2409	0.2430	0.2337	0.2331	0.2356	0.2301	0.2298	0.2373	0.2493	0.2430	
	2016	0.1983	0.2124	0.2165	0.2188	0.2151	0.2044	0.2011	0.2197	0.2173	0.2166	
	2017	0.2446	0.2447	0.2418	0.2347	0.2516	0.2346	0.2317	0.2421	0.2414	0.2391	
	2018	0.2205	0.2342	0.2353	0.2291	0.2281	0.2271	0.2358	0.2243	0.2335	0.2342	
	2019	0.2268	0.2356	0.2246	0.2285	0.2305	0.2278	0.2234	0.2275	0.2253	0.2209	
	2020	0.2362	0.2426	0.2341	0.2348	0.2473	0.2391	0.2309	0.2496	0.2457	0.2314	
	2021	0.2302	0.2251	0.2185	0.2218	0.2170	0.2312	0.2190	0.2315	0.2217	0.2279	
	2022	0.2199	0.2187	0.2088	0.2223	0.2126	0.2240	0.2201	0.2191	0.2234	0.2193	
TIGER	2013	0.2516	0.2522	0.2499	0.2516	0.2506	0.2512	0.2499	0.2500	0.2515	0.2519	
	2014	0.2689	0.2696	0.2699	0.2707	0.2727	0.2713	0.2690	0.2733	0.2710	0.2684	
	2015	0.2779	0.2805	0.2790	0.2788	0.2835	0.2797	0.2762	0.2777	0.2740	0.2764	
	2016	0.2968	0.2963	0.2964	0.2991	0.3015	0.2969	0.2937	0.2985	0.2976	0.2962	
	2017	0.3127	0.3132	0.3081	0.3099	0.3098	0.3068	0.3046	0.3078	0.3059	0.3031	
	2018	0.2919	0.2930	0.2932	0.2940	0.2973	0.2920	0.2917	0.2953	0.2943	0.2939	
	2019	0.2992	0.3043	0.3066	0.3051	0.3044	0.3011	0.3017	0.3035	0.3053	0.3038	
	2020	0.2880	0.2928	0.2909	0.2914	0.2942	0.2908	0.2890	0.2925	0.2895	0.2894	
	2021	0.2790	0.2804	0.2808	0.2836	0.2857	0.2830	0.2812	0.2842	0.2843	0.2822	
	2022	0.2831	0.2875	0.2865	0.2868	0.2867	0.2814	0.2783	0.2803	0.2795	0.2801	

Table S9. Results between our model and the baseline models @2 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.2534	0.2539	0.2531	0.2556	0.2549	0.2540	0.2514	0.2575	0.2566	0.2551	
	2014	0.2363	0.2358	0.2381	0.2384	0.2400	0.2381	0.2349	0.2389	0.2400	0.2397	
	2015	0.2689	0.2736	0.2726	0.2742	0.2760	0.2739	0.2710	0.2775	0.2771	0.2750	
	2016	0.2332	0.2373	0.2357	0.2364	0.2386	0.2375	0.2325	0.2387	0.2375	0.2361	
	2017	0.2804	0.2809	0.2831	0.2816	0.2850	0.2824	0.2805	0.2871	0.2858	0.2846	
	2018	0.2605	0.2610	0.2613	0.2613	0.2625	0.2640	0.2581	0.2643	0.2651	0.2649	
	2019	0.2605	0.2592	0.2612	0.2583	0.2624	0.2593	0.2565	0.2626	0.2633	0.2630	
	2020	0.2701	0.2716	0.2727	0.2726	0.2743	0.2733	0.2673	0.2739	0.2722	0.2730	
	2021	0.2581	0.2586	0.2596	0.2581	0.2612	0.2595	0.2550	0.2608	0.2624	0.2598	
	2022	0.2423	0.2430	0.2441	0.2443	0.2474	0.2453	0.2422	0.2480	0.2481	0.2456	
SpEL	2013	0.3104	0.3087	0.3132	0.3079	0.3209	0.3072	0.3185	0.3095	0.3196	0.3124	
	2014	0.3011	0.2988	0.3049	0.3010	0.3093	0.2942	0.2940	0.3030	0.3000	0.3092	
	2015	0.3351	0.3357	0.3244	0.3274	0.3271	0.3306	0.3245	0.3379	0.3283	0.3390	
	2016	0.2859	0.3067	0.2954	0.2968	0.2962	0.2891	0.2907	0.2988	0.3056	0.2975	
	2017	0.3393	0.3447	0.3508	0.3501	0.3545	0.3354	0.3348	0.3483	0.3462	0.3481	
	2018	0.3151	0.3150	0.3154	0.3250	0.3212	0.3218	0.3094	0.3315	0.3268	0.3310	
	2019	0.3107	0.3273	0.3219	0.3168	0.3134	0.3108	0.3142	0.3305	0.3247	0.3221	
	2020	0.3225	0.3389	0.3231	0.3324	0.3361	0.3334	0.3231	0.3403	0.3332	0.3297	
	2021	0.3137	0.3171	0.3181	0.3168	0.3145	0.3261	0.3076	0.3225	0.3245	0.3204	
	2022	0.3063	0.2943	0.3025	0.3079	0.3145	0.3075	0.2989	0.3157	0.3162	0.3006	
TIGER	2013	0.3609	0.3603	0.3597	0.3610	0.3598	0.3582	0.3590	0.3607	0.3618	0.3617	
	2014	0.3786	0.3790	0.3771	0.3808	0.3821	0.3785	0.3778	0.3832	0.3802	0.3795	
	2015	0.3865	0.3900	0.3886	0.3890	0.3916	0.3898	0.3860	0.3900	0.3889	0.3881	
	2016	0.4126	0.4140	0.4127	0.4149	0.4164	0.4125	0.4088	0.4141	0.4136	0.4136	
	2017	0.4286	0.4302	0.4284	0.4272	0.4307	0.4245	0.4248	0.4309	0.4282	0.4268	
	2018	0.4072	0.4066	0.4087	0.4095	0.4112	0.4054	0.4048	0.4103	0.4073	0.4101	
	2019	0.4189	0.4221	0.4230	0.4213	0.4250	0.4225	0.4210	0.4244	0.4244	0.4245	
	2020	0.4018	0.4063	0.4044	0.4045	0.4072	0.4025	0.4017	0.4055	0.4048	0.4037	
	2021	0.3918	0.3941	0.3948	0.3964	0.3994	0.3954	0.3933	0.3994	0.3976	0.3964	
	2022	0.3934	0.3980	0.3976	0.3973	0.3963	0.3919	0.3880	0.3939	0.3921	0.3921	

Table S10. Results between our model and the baseline models @4 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.3479	0.3500	0.3494	0.3500	0.3549	0.3510	0.3469	0.3536	0.3554	0.3522	
	2014	0.3260	0.3289	0.3301	0.3305	0.3341	0.3302	0.3264	0.3337	0.3355	0.3327	
	2015	0.3651	0.3680	0.3693	0.3721	0.3722	0.3691	0.3673	0.3712	0.3749	0.3716	
	2016	0.3262	0.3266	0.3260	0.3277	0.3308	0.3287	0.3220	0.3287	0.3316	0.3280	
	2017	0.3800	0.3813	0.3832	0.3836	0.3861	0.3835	0.3799	0.3854	0.3861	0.3830	
	2018	0.3576	0.3570	0.3569	0.3585	0.3603	0.3600	0.3540	0.3596	0.3637	0.3593	
	2019	0.3570	0.3567	0.3596	0.3567	0.3619	0.3582	0.3546	0.3604	0.3625	0.3624	
	2020	0.3668	0.3697	0.3713	0.3729	0.3738	0.3716	0.3657	0.3722	0.3730	0.3724	
	2021	0.3540	0.3567	0.3538	0.3549	0.3609	0.3565	0.3519	0.3575	0.3599	0.3575	
	2022	0.3352	0.3362	0.3382	0.3374	0.3410	0.3391	0.3368	0.3418	0.3423	0.3410	
SpEL	2013	0.4081	0.4103	0.4155	0.4107	0.4328	0.4125	0.4111	0.4206	0.4169	0.4320	
	2014	0.3903	0.3985	0.3950	0.4009	0.4118	0.4048	0.4038	0.3974	0.4065	0.3960	
	2015	0.4395	0.4365	0.4351	0.4401	0.4473	0.4354	0.4365	0.4450	0.4357	0.4335	
	2016	0.3889	0.3933	0.4010	0.3998	0.4024	0.4024	0.4002	0.3932	0.3995	0.3880	
	2017	0.4458	0.4593	0.4531	0.4577	0.4601	0.4485	0.4505	0.4622	0.4519	0.4462	
	2018	0.4341	0.4215	0.4361	0.4352	0.4353	0.4210	0.4330	0.4267	0.4292	0.4361	
	2019	0.4274	0.4309	0.4353	0.4343	0.4387	0.4211	0.4215	0.4360	0.4268	0.4294	
	2020	0.4431	0.4424	0.4447	0.4348	0.4481	0.4413	0.4370	0.4437	0.4471	0.4332	
	2021	0.4297	0.4172	0.4196	0.4165	0.4373	0.4262	0.4137	0.4367	0.4350	0.4237	
	2022	0.4065	0.4143	0.3991	0.4023	0.4109	0.4126	0.4133	0.4084	0.4107	0.4155	
TIGER	2013	0.4768	0.4750	0.4748	0.4755	0.4752	0.4746	0.4742	0.4763	0.4764	0.4777	
	2014	0.4901	0.4927	0.4926	0.4927	0.4909	0.4891	0.4872	0.4921	0.4903	0.4913	
	2015	0.4997	0.5042	0.5037	0.5023	0.5047	0.5017	0.4996	0.5041	0.5036	0.5025	
	2016	0.5271	0.5318	0.5305	0.5309	0.5329	0.5277	0.5256	0.5312	0.5285	0.5297	
	2017	0.5441	0.5473	0.5474	0.5463	0.5479	0.5441	0.5424	0.5487	0.5457	0.5442	
	2018	0.5215	0.5232	0.5236	0.5256	0.5271	0.5231	0.5200	0.5259	0.5230	0.5256	
	2019	0.5374	0.5428	0.5439	0.5397	0.5417	0.5377	0.5364	0.5423	0.5424	0.5426	
	2020	0.5180	0.5218	0.5192	0.5176	0.5189	0.5138	0.5155	0.5201	0.5175	0.5174	
	2021	0.5073	0.5093	0.5086	0.5093	0.5112	0.5081	0.5067	0.5141	0.5118	0.5133	
	2022	0.5093	0.5126	0.5137	0.5117	0.5125	0.5097	0.5038	0.5083	0.5093	0.5100	

Table S11. Results between our model and the baseline models @8 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.4531	0.4544	0.4538	0.4565	0.4586	0.4550	0.4531	0.4574	0.4609	0.4564	
	2014	0.4314	0.4327	0.4322	0.4347	0.4385	0.4338	0.4314	0.4360	0.4409	0.4393	
	2015	0.4700	0.4721	0.4723	0.4749	0.4774	0.4749	0.4714	0.4745	0.4776	0.4761	
	2016	0.4258	0.4285	0.4296	0.4306	0.4354	0.4316	0.4260	0.4296	0.4363	0.4317	
	2017	0.4863	0.4887	0.4880	0.4906	0.4918	0.4902	0.4886	0.4898	0.4931	0.4905	
	2018	0.4616	0.4638	0.4600	0.4639	0.4656	0.4624	0.4604	0.4620	0.4657	0.4642	
	2019	0.4614	0.4663	0.4668	0.4658	0.4689	0.4670	0.4627	0.4650	0.4698	0.4695	
	2020	0.4719	0.4753	0.4762	0.4772	0.4790	0.4766	0.4730	0.4776	0.4785	0.4795	
	2021	0.4551	0.4591	0.4594	0.4602	0.4640	0.4611	0.4586	0.4609	0.4651	0.4640	
	2022	0.4396	0.4421	0.4409	0.4433	0.4454	0.4428	0.4391	0.4442	0.4473	0.4455	
SpEL	2013	0.5321	0.5425	0.5336	0.5353	0.5355	0.5303	0.5268	0.5385	0.5376	0.5383	
	2014	0.5158	0.5082	0.5131	0.5224	0.5201	0.5120	0.5027	0.5133	0.5236	0.5185	
	2015	0.5572	0.5510	0.5449	0.5557	0.5642	0.5459	0.5607	0.5482	0.5627	0.5588	
	2016	0.5118	0.5015	0.5160	0.5091	0.5144	0.5134	0.5124	0.4999	0.5228	0.5168	
	2017	0.5704	0.5785	0.5739	0.5770	0.5805	0.5718	0.5753	0.5598	0.5661	0.5720	
	2018	0.5337	0.5441	0.5473	0.5364	0.5554	0.5361	0.5482	0.5411	0.5387	0.5428	
	2019	0.5331	0.5535	0.5431	0.5415	0.5478	0.5497	0.5485	0.5466	0.5470	0.5481	
	2020	0.5589	0.5637	0.5597	0.5614	0.5648	0.5559	0.5433	0.5519	0.5523	0.5617	
	2021	0.5252	0.5304	0.5374	0.5456	0.5390	0.5418	0.5325	0.5314	0.5522	0.5344	
	2022	0.5105	0.5245	0.5150	0.5320	0.5258	0.5162	0.5221	0.5164	0.5350	0.5308	
TIGER	2013	0.5888	0.5910	0.5876	0.5890	0.5910	0.5899	0.5880	0.5888	0.5886	0.5917	
	2014	0.5973	0.6006	0.5999	0.6011	0.6004	0.5977	0.5970	0.6016	0.6003	0.6005	
	2015	0.6069	0.6105	0.6114	0.6103	0.6113	0.6091	0.6071	0.6100	0.6094	0.6120	
	2016	0.6353	0.6379	0.6378	0.6381	0.6408	0.6357	0.6345	0.6398	0.6381	0.6400	
	2017	0.6513	0.6519	0.6522	0.6504	0.6514	0.6495	0.6494	0.6511	0.6486	0.6498	
	2018	0.6289	0.6297	0.6290	0.6315	0.6340	0.6287	0.6276	0.6309	0.6285	0.6327	
	2019	0.6453	0.6480	0.6508	0.6452	0.6487	0.6455	0.6455	0.6485	0.6476	0.6517	
	2020	0.6253	0.6252	0.6252	0.6252	0.6257	0.6243	0.6232	0.6279	0.6255	0.6271	
	2021	0.6138	0.6164	0.6149	0.6152	0.6189	0.6162	0.6159	0.6228	0.6194	0.6229	
	2022	0.6195	0.6233	0.6243	0.6214	0.6207	0.6203	0.6166	0.6196	0.6173	0.6206	

Table S12. Results between our model and the baseline models @16 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.5589	0.5606	0.5615	0.5625	0.5653	0.5625	0.5614	0.5622	0.5683	0.5640	
	2014	0.5393	0.5424	0.5436	0.5450	0.5473	0.5416	0.5414	0.5443	0.5490	0.5457	
	2015	0.5774	0.5790	0.5787	0.5801	0.5813	0.5820	0.5821	0.5814	0.5838	0.5829	
	2016	0.5339	0.5377	0.5375	0.5372	0.5430	0.5396	0.5381	0.5367	0.5412	0.5389	
	2017	0.5901	0.5945	0.5952	0.5970	0.5985	0.5970	0.5966	0.5966	0.5986	0.5970	
	2018	0.5677	0.5707	0.5691	0.5710	0.5725	0.5695	0.5680	0.5700	0.5736	0.5705	
	2019	0.5715	0.5742	0.5744	0.5752	0.5772	0.5737	0.5726	0.5740	0.5774	0.5782	
	2020	0.5779	0.5806	0.5835	0.5842	0.5856	0.5817	0.5819	0.5839	0.5840	0.5849	
	2021	0.5631	0.5665	0.5662	0.5682	0.5728	0.5684	0.5667	0.5680	0.5718	0.5695	
	2022	0.5465	0.5499	0.5498	0.5514	0.5524	0.5479	0.5469	0.5498	0.5529	0.5541	
SpEL	2013	0.6296	0.6228	0.6277	0.6404	0.6316	0.6352	0.6397	0.6279	0.6365	0.6422	
	2014	0.6073	0.6098	0.6121	0.6203	0.6121	0.6203	0.6033	0.6203	0.6277	0.6063	
	2015	0.6480	0.6492	0.6482	0.6405	0.6443	0.6454	0.6429	0.6609	0.6579	0.6518	
	2016	0.5947	0.6009	0.5981	0.6037	0.6130	0.6174	0.5982	0.6100	0.6082	0.6008	
	2017	0.6690	0.6680	0.6662	0.6626	0.6731	0.6720	0.6645	0.6729	0.6620	0.6600	
	2018	0.6462	0.6472	0.6292	0.6368	0.6415	0.6393	0.6377	0.6495	0.6531	0.6395	
	2019	0.6370	0.6438	0.6362	0.6397	0.6407	0.6443	0.6516	0.6406	0.6494	0.6516	
	2020	0.6539	0.6515	0.6518	0.6566	0.6529	0.6423	0.6565	0.6622	0.6599	0.6627	
	2021	0.6354	0.6291	0.6351	0.6413	0.6341	0.6355	0.6310	0.6330	0.6371	0.6336	
	2022	0.6191	0.6215	0.6271	0.6283	0.6156	0.6164	0.6094	0.6146	0.6266	0.6277	
TIGER	2013	0.6926	0.6948	0.6924	0.6930	0.6952	0.6925	0.6917	0.6939	0.6926	0.6975	
	2014	0.6973	0.6975	0.6990	0.6989	0.6996	0.6970	0.6960	0.6988	0.6984	0.7019	
	2015	0.7074	0.7094	0.7094	0.7082	0.7124	0.7069	0.7064	0.7080	0.7074	0.7093	
	2016	0.7315	0.7321	0.7339	0.7316	0.7360	0.7320	0.7313	0.7339	0.7334	0.7352	
	2017	0.7387	0.7378	0.7401	0.7378	0.7405	0.7381	0.7379	0.7399	0.7370	0.7382	
	2018	0.7220	0.7249	0.7236	0.7243	0.7262	0.7229	0.7235	0.7229	0.7217	0.7251	
	2019	0.7400	0.7405	0.7434	0.7397	0.7425	0.7406	0.7397	0.7423	0.7415	0.7444	
	2020	0.7194	0.7187	0.7204	0.7186	0.7212	0.7200	0.7218	0.7232	0.7227	0.7249	
	2021	0.7135	0.7133	0.7127	0.7121	0.7171	0.7150	0.7153	0.7182	0.7156	0.7196	
	2022	0.7167	0.7193	0.7178	0.7164	0.7183	0.7187	0.7163	0.7181	0.7154	0.7189	

Table S13. Results between our model and the baseline models @32 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.6631	0.6651	0.6671	0.6682	0.6688	0.6688	0.6648	0.6659	0.6687	0.6684	
	2014	0.6459	0.6524	0.6515	0.6515	0.6548	0.6508	0.6492	0.6531	0.6553	0.6542	
	2015	0.6797	0.6825	0.6840	0.6839	0.6849	0.6837	0.6837	0.6830	0.6851	0.6849	
	2016	0.6425	0.6452	0.6438	0.6447	0.6471	0.6443	0.6442	0.6435	0.6463	0.6465	
	2017	0.6912	0.6955	0.6975	0.6987	0.6994	0.6982	0.6986	0.6986	0.6993	0.6982	
	2018	0.6693	0.6737	0.6720	0.6731	0.6752	0.6724	0.6710	0.6708	0.6749	0.6735	
	2019	0.6743	0.6789	0.6807	0.6805	0.6815	0.6782	0.6795	0.6797	0.6820	0.6826	
	2020	0.6813	0.6829	0.6849	0.6855	0.6878	0.6858	0.6849	0.6860	0.6862	0.6884	
	2021	0.6658	0.6703	0.6698	0.6703	0.6734	0.6716	0.6697	0.6718	0.6745	0.6734	
	2022	0.6536	0.6560	0.6570	0.6568	0.6600	0.6565	0.6565	0.6590	0.6604	0.6607	
SpEL	2013	0.7148	0.7248	0.7236	0.7270	0.7261	0.7289	0.7243	0.7341	0.7297	0.7208	
	2014	0.6996	0.7158	0.7155	0.7027	0.7214	0.7140	0.6999	0.7036	0.7099	0.7120	
	2015	0.7368	0.7446	0.7458	0.7411	0.7386	0.7526	0.7407	0.7389	0.7507	0.7480	
	2016	0.6936	0.7022	0.7054	0.7133	0.7033	0.7053	0.7124	0.7107	0.6975	0.7066	
	2017	0.7476	0.7583	0.7606	0.7633	0.7533	0.7541	0.7610	0.7547	0.7679	0.7502	
	2018	0.7233	0.7296	0.7247	0.7251	0.7279	0.7381	0.7298	0.7248	0.7370	0.7392	
	2019	0.7251	0.7358	0.7317	0.7326	0.7473	0.7425	0.7371	0.7399	0.7370	0.7407	
	2020	0.7404	0.7517	0.7484	0.7371	0.7494	0.7548	0.7408	0.7476	0.7531	0.7506	
	2021	0.7315	0.7322	0.7204	0.7231	0.7241	0.7253	0.7241	0.7407	0.7284	0.7246	
	2022	0.7202	0.7215	0.7148	0.7132	0.7189	0.7104	0.7106	0.7092	0.7253	0.7137	
TIGER	2013	0.7819	0.7833	0.7826	0.7815	0.7858	0.7820	0.7812	0.7823	0.7814	0.7860	
	2014	0.7854	0.7854	0.7879	0.7860	0.7882	0.7839	0.7857	0.7869	0.7853	0.7895	
	2015	0.7909	0.7922	0.7937	0.7920	0.7949	0.7911	0.7908	0.7919	0.7916	0.7918	
	2016	0.8122	0.8129	0.8157	0.8138	0.8166	0.8126	0.8144	0.8146	0.8141	0.8159	
	2017	0.8138	0.8142	0.8165	0.8138	0.8163	0.8140	0.8136	0.8154	0.8111	0.8139	
	2018	0.8024	0.8025	0.8042	0.8026	0.8071	0.8042	0.8039	0.8030	0.8035	0.8075	
	2019	0.8171	0.8176	0.8193	0.8175	0.8220	0.8190	0.8198	0.8202	0.8184	0.8207	
	2020	0.8001	0.8002	0.8010	0.7992	0.8039	0.8007	0.8035	0.8033	0.8023	0.8051	
	2021	0.7967	0.7974	0.8000	0.7979	0.8040	0.7994	0.7993	0.8019	0.7997	0.8031	
	2022	0.7974	0.7990	0.7985	0.7980	0.8013	0.7990	0.7989	0.8010	0.7984	0.8037	

Table S14. Results between our model and the baseline models @64 ("Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set).

		Test	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
	Train											
BLINK	2013	0.7594	0.7617	0.7625	0.7613	0.7628	0.7621	0.7614	0.7628	0.7651	0.7639	
	2014	0.7489	0.7538	0.7532	0.7537	0.7546	0.7529	0.7517	0.7541	0.7551	0.7539	
	2015	0.7731	0.7758	0.7768	0.7776	0.7766	0.7754	0.7749	0.7746	0.7780	0.7769	
	2016	0.7421	0.7449	0.7419	0.7456	0.7441	0.7434	0.7425	0.7413	0.7441	0.7440	
	2017	0.7840	0.7880	0.7890	0.7886	0.7880	0.7873	0.7864	0.7867	0.7899	0.7873	
	2018	0.7650	0.7669	0.7660	0.7660	0.7668	0.7649	0.7641	0.7657	0.7688	0.7666	
	2019	0.7695	0.7745	0.7759	0.7758	0.7764	0.7752	0.7749	0.7750	0.7770	0.7755	
	2020	0.7742	0.7764	0.7765	0.7763	0.7788	0.7760	0.7767	0.7779	0.7788	0.7793	
	2021	0.7621	0.7655	0.7659	0.7659	0.7669	0.7660	0.7640	0.7651	0.7675	0.7667	
	2022	0.7506	0.7565	0.7560	0.7550	0.7588	0.7550	0.7556	0.7562	0.7583	0.7575	
SpEL	2013	0.8156	0.8058	0.8220	0.8155	0.8169	0.8190	0.8204	0.8169	0.8144	0.8096	
	2014	0.7936	0.8021	0.8042	0.8071	0.8033	0.8041	0.8011	0.7942	0.8085	0.8102	
	2015	0.8169	0.8340	0.8209	0.8244	0.8253	0.8170	0.8341	0.8257	0.8338	0.8243	
	2016	0.7976	0.7905	0.7877	0.7877	0.8029	0.7973	0.7997	0.7969	0.7891	0.7875	
	2017	0.8438	0.8436	0.8469	0.8424	0.8422	0.8405	0.8463	0.8311	0.8405	0.8427	
	2018	0.8223	0.8249	0.8197	0.8173	0.8131	0.8220	0.8046	0.8091	0.8136	0.8186	
	2019	0.8173	0.8266	0.8273	0.8228	0.8275	0.8227	0.8322	0.8344	0.8310	0.8241	
	2020	0.8172	0.8313	0.8325	0.8222	0.8337	0.8258	0.8237	0.8197	0.8381	0.8195	
	2021	0.8099	0.8073	0.8132	0.8251	0.8130	0.8109	0.8213	0.8128	0.8117	0.8082	
	2022	0.8000	0.8153	0.7979	0.8052	0.8024	0.8027	0.8145	0.8108	0.8160	0.8148	
TIGER	2013	0.8558	0.8564	0.8556	0.8552	0.8571	0.8556	0.8554	0.8560	0.8557	0.8590	
	2014	0.8568	0.8564	0.8574	0.8556	0.8582	0.8536	0.8555	0.8556	0.8545	0.8579	
	2015	0.8597	0.8604	0.8614	0.8594	0.8643	0.8607	0.8600	0.8596	0.8585	0.8620	
	2016	0.8761	0.8764	0.8783	0.8763	0.8807	0.8774	0.8780	0.8792	0.8782	0.8796	
	2017	0.8750	0.8756	0.8766	0.8746	0.8767	0.8737	0.8741	0.8739	0.8723	0.8747	
	2018	0.8680	0.8687	0.8702	0.8706	0.8739	0.8696	0.8694	0.8692	0.8678	0.8727	
	2019	0.8784	0.8786	0.8796	0.8781	0.8802	0.8786	0.8808	0.8797	0.8788	0.8806	
	2020	0.8657	0.8666	0.8671	0.8652	0.8686	0.8664	0.8679	0.8685	0.8668	0.8693	
	2021	0.8656	0.8668	0.8686	0.8664	0.8686	0.8669	0.8677	0.8682	0.8662	0.8688	
	2022	0.8652	0.8685	0.8672	0.8654	0.8683	0.8663	0.8652	0.8665	0.8654	0.8679	

5. ADDITIONAL RESULTS - MITIGATING TEMPORAL DEGRADATION

Table S15 to Table S18 illuminate the effectiveness of our model in mitigating temporal degradation using results derived from the expanded TempEL dataset. In Table S15 and Table S16, we use "Extended TempEL: New entities" as the training set. In Table S17 and Table S18, we use "Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as the training set. Each column in the table represents the years' gap between the training and testing datasets, as denoted by the digits from 0 to 9. For instance, 0 implies that training and testing datasets come from the same year, while 9 indicates that the model was trained in 2013 and tested in 2022. The rows are divided based on various metrics, includes @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32 and @64. "Boost" displays a comparison between our model TIGER and SpEL model, calculated as $\text{Boost} = \frac{\text{Our Model's Result} - \text{Baseline Model's Result}}{\text{Baseline Model's Result}}$.

Table S15 and Table S17 show models' performance on the "Only Forward" setting. "Only Forward" means the results include only one scenario: the model is trained in the past and tested in the future. Table S16 and Table S18 show models' performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting. "Forward and Backward" means the results include two scenarios: training in the past and testing in the future, and training in the future and testing in the past. For instance, in Table S15, when @1 and the gap is 9, our model's result under "Only Forward" is 0.2304, representing only the situation of training in 2013 and testing in 2022. However, in Table S16 under "Forward and Backward," our model's result is 0.1914, which is the average of two situations: training in 2013 and testing in 2022, and training in 2022 and testing in 2013. It is worth noting that when the gap is 0, it means the training and testing datasets come from the same year. Thus, the "Only Forward" and "Forward and Backward" values are equal.

Table S15. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Only Forward" setting using "Extended TempEL: New entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1333	0.1340	0.1340	0.1357	0.1349	0.1360	0.1348	0.1357	0.1346	0.1433
	SpEL	0.1733	0.1695	0.1765	0.1771	0.1699	0.1720	0.1723	0.1790	0.1796	0.1933
	TIGER	0.2032	0.2076	0.2086	0.2163	0.2158	0.2232	0.2211	0.2221	0.2149	0.2304
	Boost (%)	17.23	22.46	18.22	22.11	27.04	29.76	28.32	24.04	19.66	19.19
@2	BLINK	0.1994	0.1999	0.2004	0.2021	0.2013	0.2027	0.2009	0.2014	0.1996	0.2117
	SpEL	0.2444	0.2455	0.2504	0.2535	0.2513	0.2447	0.2484	0.2481	0.2496	0.2617
	TIGER	0.2948	0.3009	0.3018	0.3114	0.3101	0.3201	0.3167	0.3185	0.3102	0.3301
	Boost (%)	20.65	22.55	20.54	22.82	23.41	30.82	27.46	28.39	24.30	26.14
@4	BLINK	0.2794	0.2789	0.2804	0.2825	0.2809	0.2837	0.2802	0.2813	0.2785	0.2952
	SpEL	0.3324	0.3411	0.3379	0.3396	0.3425	0.3457	0.3402	0.3446	0.3385	0.3652
	TIGER	0.3975	0.4042	0.4060	0.4161	0.4143	0.4250	0.4223	0.4244	0.4139	0.4376
	Boost (%)	19.56	18.50	20.16	22.52	20.96	22.96	24.13	23.16	22.27	19.82
@8	BLINK	0.3720	0.3717	0.3735	0.3752	0.3724	0.3745	0.3713	0.3713	0.3687	0.3883
	SpEL	0.4370	0.4439	0.4422	0.4437	0.4424	0.4445	0.4438	0.4380	0.4437	0.4483
	TIGER	0.5050	0.5122	0.5133	0.5234	0.5215	0.5326	0.5298	0.5311	0.5215	0.5453
	Boost (%)	15.57	15.39	16.07	17.95	17.88	19.82	19.37	21.26	17.53	21.64
@16	BLINK	0.4717	0.4716	0.4724	0.4737	0.4705	0.4728	0.4693	0.4681	0.4660	0.4848
	SpEL	0.5437	0.5427	0.5499	0.5452	0.5422	0.5448	0.5368	0.5415	0.5360	0.5448
	TIGER	0.6109	0.6163	0.6175	0.6257	0.6235	0.6353	0.6335	0.6334	0.6250	0.6489
	Boost (%)	12.35	13.56	12.29	14.77	15.00	16.60	18.01	16.97	16.60	19.11
@32	BLINK	0.5747	0.5745	0.5743	0.5751	0.5715	0.5737	0.5696	0.5678	0.5652	0.5855
	SpEL	0.6407	0.6412	0.6393	0.6451	0.6398	0.6397	0.6371	0.6345	0.6352	0.6555
	TIGER	0.7081	0.7122	0.7132	0.7188	0.7173	0.7284	0.7262	0.7254	0.7206	0.7401
	Boost (%)	10.51	11.08	11.55	11.42	12.11	13.86	13.99	14.33	13.45	12.91
@64	BLINK	0.6741	0.6739	0.6735	0.6742	0.6712	0.6734	0.6698	0.6670	0.6651	0.6832
	SpEL	0.7331	0.7350	0.7310	0.7370	0.7279	0.7354	0.7323	0.7270	0.7201	0.7432
	TIGER	0.7920	0.7951	0.7955	0.7993	0.7977	0.8057	0.8043	0.8030	0.7996	0.8169
	Boost (%)	8.03	8.17	8.83	8.46	9.59	9.57	9.83	10.45	11.04	9.92

Table S16. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting using "Extended TempEL: New entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1333	0.1326	0.1331	0.1332	0.1329	0.1325	0.1321	0.1305	0.1306	0.1350
	SpEL	0.1733	0.1687	0.1737	0.1725	0.1688	0.1685	0.1709	0.1672	0.1731	0.1750
	TIGER	0.2032	0.2037	0.2040	0.2052	0.2028	0.2031	0.2018	0.1968	0.1960	0.1914
	Boost (%)	17.23	20.74	17.42	18.98	20.17	20.53	18.10	17.70	13.18	9.37
@2	BLINK	0.1994	0.1985	0.1992	0.1996	0.1990	0.1981	0.1973	0.1957	0.1955	0.2015
	SpEL	0.2444	0.2457	0.2461	0.2482	0.2465	0.2401	0.2423	0.2390	0.2430	0.2365
	TIGER	0.2948	0.2958	0.2961	0.2978	0.2944	0.2942	0.2926	0.2870	0.2866	0.2808
	Boost (%)	20.65	20.39	20.29	19.99	19.43	22.50	20.79	20.09	17.97	18.74
@4	BLINK	0.2794	0.2777	0.2793	0.2796	0.2787	0.2787	0.2771	0.2748	0.2741	0.2830
	SpEL	0.3324	0.3344	0.3356	0.3354	0.3404	0.3387	0.3321	0.3298	0.3266	0.3380
	TIGER	0.3975	0.3985	0.3991	0.4005	0.3970	0.3967	0.3959	0.3886	0.3880	0.3822
	Boost (%)	19.56	19.18	18.94	19.43	16.63	17.13	19.19	17.84	18.83	13.09
@8	BLINK	0.3720	0.3704	0.3721	0.3731	0.3713	0.3708	0.3692	0.3653	0.3652	0.3751
	SpEL	0.4370	0.4398	0.4421	0.4409	0.4388	0.4398	0.4354	0.4319	0.4277	0.4201
	TIGER	0.5050	0.5061	0.5063	0.5082	0.5046	0.5042	0.5042	0.4960	0.4957	0.4895
	Boost (%)	15.57	15.08	14.54	15.26	15.00	14.64	15.80	14.83	15.89	16.51
@16	BLINK	0.4717	0.4702	0.4720	0.4727	0.4709	0.4703	0.4689	0.4642	0.4644	0.4724
	SpEL	0.5437	0.5402	0.5414	0.5419	0.5392	0.5383	0.5364	0.5309	0.5294	0.5274
	TIGER	0.6109	0.6111	0.6116	0.6126	0.6088	0.6096	0.6105	0.6021	0.6015	0.5974
	Boost (%)	12.35	13.12	12.95	13.04	12.90	13.26	13.81	13.41	13.62	13.27
@32	BLINK	0.5747	0.5730	0.5745	0.5748	0.5729	0.5723	0.5711	0.5659	0.5657	0.5745
	SpEL	0.6407	0.6419	0.6420	0.6441	0.6412	0.6393	0.6336	0.6309	0.6332	0.6395
	TIGER	0.7081	0.7080	0.7087	0.7090	0.7055	0.7069	0.7079	0.7009	0.7000	0.6971
	Boost (%)	10.51	10.29	10.39	10.07	10.03	10.58	11.73	11.09	10.55	9.01
@64	BLINK	0.6741	0.6731	0.6741	0.6748	0.6732	0.6730	0.6723	0.6674	0.6665	0.6736
	SpEL	0.7331	0.7320	0.7316	0.7348	0.7307	0.7320	0.7311	0.7257	0.7190	0.7186
	TIGER	0.7920	0.7920	0.7925	0.7921	0.7895	0.7902	0.7923	0.7856	0.7849	0.7841
	Boost (%)	8.03	8.20	8.32	7.81	8.05	7.95	8.38	8.25	9.17	9.12

Table S17. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Only Forward" setting using "Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1760	0.1770	0.1776	0.1767	0.1755	0.1755	0.1703	0.1764	0.1682	0.1741
	SpEL	0.2289	0.2266	0.2247	0.2215	0.2273	0.2243	0.2245	0.2264	0.2183	0.2264
	TIGER	0.2860	0.2862	0.2870	0.2862	0.2827	0.2797	0.2734	0.2658	0.2600	0.2519
	Boost (%)	24.95	26.31	27.71	29.22	24.39	24.71	21.76	17.40	19.08	11.26
@2	BLINK	0.2586	0.2600	0.2608	0.2596	0.2589	0.2577	0.2509	0.2575	0.2482	0.2551
	SpEL	0.3186	0.3185	0.3189	0.3194	0.3193	0.3186	0.3118	0.3162	0.3144	0.3124
	TIGER	0.3996	0.3997	0.4010	0.4006	0.3961	0.3933	0.3862	0.3763	0.3707	0.3617
	Boost (%)	25.40	25.53	25.74	25.44	24.07	23.46	23.84	19.03	17.89	15.78
@4	BLINK	0.3548	0.3568	0.3569	0.3552	0.3544	0.3526	0.3459	0.3536	0.3441	0.3522
	SpEL	0.4238	0.4262	0.4254	0.4256	0.4259	0.4214	0.4081	0.4202	0.4065	0.4320
	TIGER	0.5153	0.5156	0.5160	0.5154	0.5111	0.5077	0.4999	0.4897	0.4839	0.4777
	Boost (%)	21.59	20.96	21.29	21.12	20.00	20.48	22.51	16.54	19.04	10.58
@8	BLINK	0.4594	0.4617	0.4622	0.4601	0.4585	0.4575	0.4496	0.4581	0.4501	0.4564
	SpEL	0.5394	0.5421	0.5448	0.5372	0.5362	0.5352	0.5299	0.5403	0.5281	0.5383
	TIGER	0.6232	0.6240	0.6238	0.6235	0.6195	0.6170	0.6098	0.6004	0.5946	0.5917
	Boost (%)	15.54	15.11	14.50	16.06	15.54	15.28	15.07	11.12	12.59	9.92
@16	BLINK	0.5668	0.5689	0.5695	0.5683	0.5658	0.5647	0.5571	0.5647	0.5570	0.5640
	SpEL	0.6382	0.6369	0.6420	0.6391	0.6344	0.6335	0.6297	0.6358	0.6214	0.6422
	TIGER	0.7192	0.7205	0.7204	0.7195	0.7158	0.7136	0.7083	0.7005	0.6973	0.6975
	Boost (%)	12.69	13.12	12.21	12.59	12.83	12.64	12.48	10.18	12.21	8.61
@32	BLINK	0.6717	0.6729	0.6735	0.6724	0.6699	0.6691	0.6624	0.6687	0.6615	0.6684
	SpEL	0.7308	0.7318	0.7305	0.7351	0.7331	0.7231	0.7213	0.7307	0.7209	0.7208
	TIGER	0.8022	0.8026	0.8020	0.8021	0.7990	0.7975	0.7939	0.7865	0.7855	0.7860
	Boost (%)	9.77	9.67	9.80	9.11	8.98	10.29	10.07	7.64	8.96	9.05
@64	BLINK	0.7666	0.7676	0.7681	0.7664	0.7647	0.7640	0.7594	0.7649	0.7595	0.7639
	SpEL	0.8169	0.8181	0.8197	0.8149	0.8185	0.8155	0.8090	0.8166	0.8123	0.8096
	TIGER	0.8680	0.8680	0.8680	0.8678	0.8658	0.8647	0.8623	0.8575	0.8568	0.8590
	Boost (%)	6.25	6.10	5.90	6.49	5.78	6.03	6.59	5.01	5.48	6.10

Table S18. Temporal degradation mitigation performance on the "Forward and Backward" setting using "Extended TempEL: Continual entities" as training dataset.

		0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
@1	BLINK	0.1760	0.1765	0.1779	0.1766	0.1775	0.1764	0.1731	0.1755	0.1691	0.1682
	SpEL	0.2289	0.2266	0.2268	0.2254	0.2286	0.2246	0.2260	0.2249	0.2214	0.2232
	TIGER	0.2860	0.2879	0.2893	0.2905	0.2889	0.2856	0.2816	0.2754	0.2716	0.2675
	Boost (%)	24.95	27.05	27.53	28.88	26.40	27.15	24.60	22.46	22.69	19.87
@2	BLINK	0.2586	0.2592	0.2610	0.2591	0.2613	0.2586	0.2549	0.2576	0.2494	0.2487
	SpEL	0.3186	0.3190	0.3212	0.3185	0.3205	0.3190	0.3154	0.3151	0.3092	0.3094
	TIGER	0.3996	0.4018	0.4038	0.4048	0.4026	0.3993	0.3953	0.3871	0.3828	0.3776
	Boost (%)	25.40	25.96	25.73	27.09	25.60	25.18	25.33	22.84	23.80	22.05
@4	BLINK	0.3548	0.3555	0.3572	0.3554	0.3580	0.3545	0.3502	0.3537	0.3446	0.3437
	SpEL	0.4238	0.4257	0.4267	0.4275	0.4286	0.4244	0.4155	0.4200	0.4142	0.4193
	TIGER	0.5153	0.5175	0.5189	0.5198	0.5180	0.5144	0.5099	0.5017	0.4969	0.4935
	Boost (%)	21.59	21.57	21.63	21.58	20.87	21.20	22.72	19.45	19.96	17.71
@8	BLINK	0.4594	0.4607	0.4623	0.4600	0.4626	0.4597	0.4547	0.4577	0.4494	0.4480
	SpEL	0.5394	0.5419	0.5425	0.5406	0.5409	0.5394	0.5357	0.5375	0.5265	0.5244
	TIGER	0.6232	0.6253	0.6267	0.6274	0.6261	0.6223	0.6182	0.6112	0.6066	0.6056
	Boost (%)	15.54	15.39	15.52	16.07	15.74	15.36	15.40	13.70	15.22	15.48
@16	BLINK	0.5668	0.5679	0.5696	0.5680	0.5696	0.5670	0.5623	0.5647	0.5568	0.5553
	SpEL	0.6382	0.6362	0.6385	0.6359	0.6388	0.6366	0.6338	0.6363	0.6249	0.6307
	TIGER	0.7192	0.7214	0.7227	0.7230	0.7213	0.7181	0.7151	0.7087	0.7068	0.7071
	Boost (%)	12.69	13.39	13.18	13.69	12.92	12.80	12.82	11.38	13.11	12.12
@32	BLINK	0.6717	0.6721	0.6737	0.6724	0.6734	0.6709	0.6667	0.6691	0.6612	0.6610
	SpEL	0.7308	0.7320	0.7315	0.7315	0.7316	0.7265	0.7245	0.7299	0.7237	0.7205
	TIGER	0.8022	0.8034	0.8039	0.8047	0.8026	0.8008	0.7989	0.7926	0.7917	0.7917
	Boost (%)	9.77	9.74	9.90	10.01	9.71	10.23	10.27	8.59	9.39	9.88
@64	BLINK	0.7666	0.7670	0.7681	0.7669	0.7678	0.7661	0.7630	0.7651	0.7594	0.7573
	SpEL	0.8169	0.8172	0.8197	0.8177	0.8204	0.8187	0.8129	0.8120	0.8125	0.8048
	TIGER	0.8680	0.8687	0.8693	0.8697	0.8682	0.8672	0.8660	0.8620	0.8619	0.8621
	Boost (%)	6.25	6.30	6.05	6.36	5.82	5.93	6.54	6.16	6.09	7.12

6. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF DIFFERENT MODELS

Figure S2 displays recall@N results from the Expanded TempEL dataset. We assessed our proposed model against the baseline bi-encoder using recall metrics. The x-axis indicates the year gap between training and testing sets, while the y-axis represents the recall rate. Overall, our model consistently outperforms the baseline models.

Fig. S2. The improvement in the metrics @1, @2, @4, @8, @16, @32 and @64.

It is also worth noting that the improvement effect of our model diminishes gradually as the metric threshold shifts from @1 to @64, as shown in Figure S3. The x-axis denotes the year gap between training and testing datasets, and the y-axis represents the improvement margin of our model compared to the SpEL model. The solid line represents the model trained on "Extended TempEL: New Entities," while the dashed line indicates the model trained on "Extended TempEL: Continual Entities."

Fig. S3. Different of Recall changes as the metric changes.